

Women Empowerment and Gender Justice Indian and International Perspective

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Introduction:

According to Indian Law Indian women got equal opportunities similar to Indian men. According to Indian custom, Traditions, rites, rituals, mostly women become very common in India. Women Empowerment is now adays very essential. Women empowerment is increasing women power, decision making powers in social, economic, political aspects. Equal opportunities in work, Education, Financial control, political voice and women empowerment important for freedom from violence.

Gender Justice:

Discrimination between men and women is happening till now. Systematic inequalities and injustice between genders recognizing diverse identities women need protection from mental, Physical abuse. Dowery death also very common in Indian society. Women should get equal participation in politics and economy. Gender based discrimination and violence should be eliminated. In India patriarchal family system is very popular. In some rural areas patriarchal norms and custom tradition practices honor killing is still happening.

Many countries thinking of gender justice and women empowerment in different aspects. Women's facing all kinds of discrimination. Universal Declaration of Human Rights Charter, International covenants and Conventions, Women Empowerment have many aspects.

Women empowerment is multi-faced concept. Empowerment of Women means give

respect to them. Power to dominate others especially male dominant nature is very famous in India.

History of Women Empowerment:

Many women's customs famous in India for example Durga, Saraswati, Kali, Laxmi etc. Patriarchal society is very famous in India. History of women empowerment –

Social reformers very important such as Raja Rammohan Roy, Swami Dayananda Saraswati they played important role in social reforms (Sati Abolition Act of 1829, Child Marriage Restraint Act of 1929, Widow Remarriage Act 1856 is very essential).

Women Empowerment is very essential in India:

- a) Economic Empowerment- Economic independence and strength very essential. Women should focus on economically strong participate freely in the economy.
- b) Empowerment of women political background- Women's they should have political Empowerment. Women should focus on political process and they should be decision making.
- c) Gender Equality- Gender Equality means equal rights, opportunities and responsibilities of women and men.
- d) Women's organizations- Women Organization include women's Indian Association, Bharat Mahila Parishad etc.

Gender Justice Principles and Policy:

Gender Justice is universally recognized human rights. Gender Justice means giving equal opportunities to men's and women's. Equal representation and participation of women and men at all levels in decision making position, we need to remove gender based biased, violence.

Indian Constitution:

Preamble is the main of Indian Constitution. Main aim and objective of Indian constitution to give equal opportunities to all Indians Irrespect of race, caste, sex, religion. Preamble of Indian Constitution starts from We the people of India means all men and women of all caste, religions, etc.

Fundamental Rights: Many nations for example India, using constitutional provisions to give equal rights to women's. This is good for women's empowerment and for social justice.

Women Empowerment: Women empowerment is very essential nowadays. Women should be financially and intellectually should be sound. Economic, Political, Social and Cultural women should be well prepared. Women's means equal representation in governance, decision making. Freedom from discrimination, violence and harmful assault, Mental physical abuse. Women should get better education and healthcare.

Gender Justice: Gender Justice are good for same rights, Opportunities, and responsibilities. Women's all human rights and laws should respectfully protected. Women's discrimination is occurs because of customs and traditions in India. Indian family is patriarchal attitudes that showing male dominance. It is focusing on negative thoughts for women empowerment. According to Indian Law Indian Law Indian women considered as a secondary. Women should get equal respect and opportunities like men's.

Importance of Women's empowerment: It is very essential for gender justice. Promotion of fairness is also very essential. Equity of all

genders is very essentials for better health, stronger economies etc it is very essential for development of society.

Examples in India:

Constitutional provisions: Art. 14, Art. 15, Art. 16, 21 and 31 (a) is good for Equality, prohibit discrimination. Its good for women to protect equal rights to women's. Global initiatives also essential for women's empowerment. Gender Equality is very essential for women's like men's.

Fundamental Rights:

- Art. 14 Equality before law.
- Art. 15 (1)- The State not to discriminate against any citizen on grounds only on Race, Religion, Race, Caste, Sex, Place of birth or any of them.
- Art. 15(3)- The State to make any Special provision in favor of women and children.
- Directive Principles of State Policy (Part IV)- Art 39(a)- The State to direct policy towards securing for men and women equally the right to an adequate means of livelihood.
- Art 39(a)- Equal pay for Equal work for both men and women.
- Art 42- The State to make provisions for securing just and human conditions of work for maternity relief.

The state should protect weaker sections of the people and protect from social Injustice.

Fundamental Duty (Part IV A):

To promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India and renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women Art. 51(A) (e).

Women have the rights to be respected and treated as equal citizens. Sexual harassment of women at workplace results in violation of Fundamental rights of "Gender Equality" and the Right to life and liberty.

International Convention treaties on gender Equalities. The covenant on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against

women (CEDAW) 1979 is the United Nations Landmark treaty marking the struggle for women's right. It has been ruled that human rights for women comprehends gender equality and it is also traceable to the Convention for Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against women.

Bodhisattwa Gautam- The Court observed that women have the right to control over his body organs and his "Person" under Art 21. It can also said to be including the complete right of a woman over her reproductive organs.

Vishakha the Court took a serious note of the increasing menace of sexual harassment at workplace.

Gender Equality:

As per the UN women, Gender Equality refers to the equal Rights, Responsibilities and opportunities of women and men, girls, boys.

Men and women they have same rights and chance, Opportunities to the women.

Women's empowerment: Women empowerment is depend on social, economic, political aspects on all societies. Women should be protected from gender based violence, discrimination in workplace not giving equality means inequalities.

Beti Bachao Beti Padhao is very essential in India. Women's Empowerment is very essential for the Indian development. Indian Society is patriarchal society and male dominating nature.

Women empowerment is very essential in India:

Economic Empowerment: Economic independence and strength very essential. Women should focus on economic empowerment. Women they should have political empowerment. Women should focus on political process and they should have decision making process.

Gender Equality: Gender equality means equal rights, opportunities and responsibilities to men and women.

Women organizations: Women organization include women Indian Association, Bharat Mahila Parishad.

Conclusion:

Women Justice and empowerment is fundamental human rights. Women suffering many problems for e.g Dowery, sexual abuse etc. Women should get rid from such kind of mental, Physical, Sexual harassment.

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